

Sansepolcro and its astronomical orientation

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Abstract: Here we discuss the layout of Sansepolcro in Tuscany. It seems that it is based on an orientation according to the sunrise on winter solstice. It is also interesting to observe that the Cathedral has a specific astronomical orientation too. It is aligned along the southernmost direction of the moonrise on a minor lunar standstill.

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Introduction

Sansepolcro is a town located in the Italian Province of Arezzo, Tuscany. It was the birthplace of a famous painter, Piero della Francesca, and of the mathematician Luca Pacioli. According to a local tradition, the core of Sansepolcro was established by two pilgrims of the tenth century, Arcano and Egidio, that founded there an oratory after their return from the Holy Land [1-3]. In this oratory, which was also the shrine for the relics they brought from the Holy Sepulchre and other places of the Holy Land, they lived a monastic life [1-3]. The construction of a related abbey, built from 1012 to 1049 and dedicated to the Four Evangelists and the Holy Sepulchre, is the first historical mention of Sansepolcro. The relics from the Holy Land are today in the Cathedral of the town [4], which is the abbey as it was rebuilt in the late 13th century. In 1520, pope Leo X established the diocese of Sansepolcro, and therefore the abbey became its cathedral and was re-dedicated to the city's patron, St. John the Evangelist [4,5].

Figure 1: Sansepolcro (Courtesy Wikimapia). In the past, the town was surrounded by fortifications.

For what concerns the remote history of Sansepolcro, it was in the XV century that the place was identified with the roman center of Biturgia, mentioned by Claudius Ptolemy in his Geography [3,6]. Let us also note that, on the foundation of Sansepolcro, an interesting hypothesis was given by Vincenzo Benini. Benini considered Sansepolcro founded in the place of a roman castrum, abandoned after the crisis of the roman empire. To support his hypothesis, Benini is mentioning a roman monument and the layout of the town which is like that of a castrum [7]. “Dopo la pubblicazione di questa ipotesi (1978), l'arch. Giovanni Cecconi, in due studi apparsi nel 1992 e nel 1994, ha proposto la tesi dell'origine del Borgo, poi Sansepolcro, dal vicus romano di Voconianus (località Boccognano)” [3,8,9].

In the Figure 1, we can see the layout of Sansepolcro. It is clear that, in the past, the town was surrounded by fortifications. In [3], we can read that the last fortifications were added to the town in the XVI century by Giuliano da Sangallo.

Of Sansepolcro, here we discuss the astronomical orientation of its layout. It seems that it is based on an orientation according to the sunrise on winter solstice. It is also interesting to observe that the Cathedral has a specific astronomical orientation too. It is aligned along the southernmost direction of the moonrise on a minor lunar standstill.

Figure 2: Thanks to Suncalc.org we can see the directions of sunrise and sunset on the winter solstice, given on the Google Map showing the Cathedral of Sansepolcro. The direction of the noon is also given, and also a line representing the motion of the sun during the day.

The orientation of the Cathedral

As told in [5], it is supposed that the first church - built where today there is the Cathedral - had a solstice orientation. That is, it was aligned along the direction of the sunrise on the winter solstice. The building that we see today, built in the late 13th century, has lost this original orientation, as shown by the Figure 2. However, the Cathedral has maintained a reference to the winter solstice through its dedication. As previously told, it is dedicated to Saint John, apostle and evangelist, and the Catholic Church celebrates his Feast on December 27, close therefore to the winter solstice.

Using Suncalc.org, that is the software that we used for the Figure 2, we can see that the building has an orientation corresponding to the sunrise on about 15 November. As shown in several publications, it is easy to find astronomical orientations of churches and cathedrals and possible alignments along the directions of the sunrise [10-29]. Therefore, it is reasonable that the original church and the Cathedral that we see today in Sansepolcro had been oriented along the direction of

the sunrise (on the winter solstice the original church and on 15 November the Cathedral). However we have to note that another possibility exists concerning the building that we see today. And it is the following. The Cathedral of the late 13th century could have been oriented according to the southernmost possible direction of the moonrise on a minor lunar standstill (see Figure 3).

Let us remember that the moon has an apparent motion in the sky, which is more complex than that of the sun. We have that the sunrise direction oscillates between the two solstice positions during a year, whereas the moon does the same during a nodal period (about 27 days). Moreover, the moon has a period – the lunar standstill period (18.613 years) – on which the values of the extreme directions (standstills) are changing. In this manner there are major and minor standstills, of which we can calculate moonrise/moonset directions. These directions are depending on the latitude. For a latitude of about 45° , like that of Torino for instance, we have that the minor and major northernmost moonrise azimuths (directions) are 47.40° and 65.65° (angles are given from true north). The minor and major southernmost moonrise azimuths are 116.35° and 132.58° . The azimuths of sunrise on summer and winter solstices are between these lunar azimuths.

During the year 2015 the moon had minor standstills. Using the Photographer's Ephemeris software (Figure 3), we can see that the Cathedral of Sansepolcro is aligned along the southernmost moonrise direction on 18 October 2015, a minor lunar standstill. So, it is possible that the building had been oriented according to the moonrise and not to the sunrise (examples of orientations according to the moonrise are given in [30-41]).

Figure 3: Thanks to the Photographer's Ephemeris, we can see the southern moonrise direction (blue line) on a minor lunar standstill. The yellow lines are referring to sunrise and sunset directions.

The orientation of the town

We have to do another important observation. It is possible that the original church, before the building of the Cathedral, was aligned along the streets of the town. Actually, we can see from the Figure 4 that the town is oriented along the direction of the sunrise on the winter solstice. Solstitial orientations are easily found in the town-planning of several Roman towns [42-48]. Therefore, it is possible that Sansepolcro has maintained in its medieval layout the orientation of the Roman center of Biturgia. Or, as told in [8,9], it is possible that Sansepolcro has maintained the orientation of a Roman Castrum or a Roman Vicus. Actually, examples of Roman castra astronomically oriented according to the solstices exist, as shown in [49,50], and it is well-known that many Roman towns evolved from their original military castra [42]. Being the orientation along the sunrise on a solstice displayed by many Roman towns and castra, it is therefore possible to argue that Sansepolcro had maintained, in its medieval layout, the orientation of an antecedent Roman site.

Figure 4: Using again Suncalc.org, we can see the directions of sunrise and sunset on the winter solstice, given on the Google Map of Sansepolcro.

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